

Warpage, A Nightmare for Composite Parts Producers

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ABSTRACT

Warpage of composite parts due to design and fabrication methods has always been a problem in making first production article because the factors which influence this phenomenon are highly indetermined. Factors influencing warpage of parts, i.e. design, tooling, fabrication plans, are examined in detail and the possibilities of a positive approach to correct the phenomenon are described.

INTRODUCTION

The final shape of cured composite parts is often different from the geometry of the lay-up mandrel. This deformed geometry is called out as "warpage". As the phenomenon is tied to the differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) existing between the fibers and the resin of the matrix, it is more accentuated for the carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) than for the fiberglass composites. Even though quite often the CFRP deformation can be eliminated with the application of low assembling loads, it is still a substantial problem on those parts that are either extremely stiff or whose periphery is not completely fastened to the assembly structure. That's the case of primary structures and airplane control surfaces, like spoilers and ailerons, that are assembled to the wing structure on one side only. Warpage is still a barely understood phenomenon, so it is a true nightmare for CFRP manufacturers. The consequence is quite often the choice of tools which are very costly and not suitable for high rate production : i.e. CFRP mandrels, even when they are not really necessary. Besides, even the choice of high cost tools does not always assure good results. So various preliminary trials must be made, before producing the first article, requiring a lot of effort and time. The in depth study of the warpage problem and a better understanding of its causes will avoid emotional decisions and therefore will reduce costs and time. This will be the workhorse for a wider utilization of CFRP technology.

TEXT

Generalities

The experience gathered during the phases of development and production of CFRP aircraft components showed that the warpage besides being tied to the part design, is also strongly dependent on manufacturing variables as material of the tool and the fabrication technique.

Design dependence of warpage

The consequence of CTE's differences between the fibers and the matrix, is a thermal expansion mismatch between plies with different fiber orientations. Keeping this in mind, the designer tries to project a lay-up that is symmetrical and balanced as much as possible. Naturally this is not always achievable, due to weight and configuration needs. So the parts are often born on the drawing board with a tensional unbalance and a consequent tendency to warp. This potential deformation must be carefully considered while designing the tool and choosing the fabrication methods. This tensional status, inherent with the design, can be evaluated using the classical laminated plate theory (1) (2) for small panels or the deflection plate theory for large panels (3).

Manufacturing dependency of warpage

The influence of the tooling materials is due to their CTE's, generally higher than those of the CFRP's. During the warm-up phase of the curing process, the lay-up is stretched by the tool expansion, due to the pressure acting on the part. During the cooling phase of the process, the tool shrinks more than the cured part so, the final dimensions of the part are usually longer than the uncured dimensions. On sandwich parts, the CTE differences influence considerable the warpage phenomenon. In fact the tool side skin is directly stretched by the tool expansion, while the effect on the bag side skin is dampened by the interposed honeycomb core. The different stress conditions in the two skins will cause the warpage phenomenon.

Laminate test panels. The quantitative stretching effect on the tool side skin was evaluated by manufacturing 4800 mm long by 75 mm wide specimens. The study included the following variables :

Specimen material : a) unidirectional tape (U.D.) with 145 g/m² graphite areal weight, 42% resin content; b) 8 harness satin fabric (8H) with 3000 elementary filament tows and 70 tows per 25.4 mm of width, 35% resin content.

Lay-up orientation : a) U.D. 0° oriented; b) U.D. 0°-90° alternatively oriented; c) U.D. + 45° oriented ; d) 8H fabric + 45° oriented; e) 8H fabric 0° oriented.

Tool material : a) aluminum b) steel.

Releasing agent : a) Wrightlon A 4000 sheet (FEP); b) one teflon sheet; c) two teflon sheets.

Layer's splicing : 8H fabric layers 0° or + 45° oriented, with splicing length variable between 25 and 1200 mm, as shown in fig. 1.

Material mixing : mixing of 8H fabric and U.D. layers.

Multiple thermal cycles : some specimens subjected to 4 additional curing cycles.

The U.D. laminates were manufactured utilizing 8 layers; the 8H fabric laminates were made with 4 layers.

In fig. 2 are summarized test results for various lay-up's on steel and aluminum mandrel.

0° oriented unidirectional tape is characterized by a very low permanent deformation. The resulting average value is about 0.04%, independently of the tool material (steel or aluminum). Substantially the tape doesn't follow the tool expansion. There's a small growth due to flattening of waves or wrinkles originated in the lay-up operations.

The largest deformation was experienced with + 45° oriented tape or fabric laid on aluminum tool. The resulting average value was about 0.3%. The linear growth measured for these specimens with fiber interrupted in the measu~~r~~ement direction is practically correspondent to the effect of CTE differences between the aluminum tool and CFRP laminate. The thermal expansion of the tool carries out the fibers that are interrupted.

The linear growth of specimens with 0° oriented 8H fabric on aluminum tool was about 0.15%. This value is intermediate between the ones obtained on 0° tape and + 45° tape or fabric specimens. The fibers are not interrupted, so they can't follow completely the tool expansion. There is a simply flattening effect of the waves in the fabric (fig. 3).

The linear growth on steel tool of + 45° oriented tape or fabric laminates and 0° oriented fabric laminates was about 0.11% (fig. 2). This value practically equals the theoretical value correspondent to the CTE difference between the steel tool and the CFRP laminate. The explanation of these coincident values for both the 0° and + 45° oriented laminates is given by the fabric capability of being elongated more than 0.11%.

The analysis, run on the different releasing media, showed no depend~~e~~ncy of the linear growth phenomenon on this parameter.

The study of the influence of the splices in the specimens made on aluminum tool, showed no influence of the splicing on + 45° oriented layers. Differently the influence of this parameter was heavy for the 0° tape laminates and light for 0° fabric laminates (fig. 4) because the growth value for unspliced 0° layers is lower than the value estimated on the basis of CTE differences.

When mixing tape and fabric in the laminates, substantially there was no linear growth. When the fabric was laid against the tool, there was a growth limited to this layer, practically indential to that on all fabric laminates. When the tape was laid against the tool, there was no growth.

Repeated curing cycles showed a linear growth of about 0.24% for both + 45° oriented tape and fabric laminates. This value was practically constant for each cycle. The dimensions of 0° tape or fabric laminates, were not changed by repeated thermal cycles.

Sandwich test panels. 4500 mm long, 305 mm wide specimens were made with different manufacturing methods, to evaluate the different conditions of the two skins. The skins were constituted by four plies of 0° oriented 8H fabric, with no splices. The following different methods of processing were utilized : curing of the skins, precuring of one skin, precuring of both skins. Two kinds of lay-up mandrels were utilized : aluminum mandrel; 0° oriented U.D. tape laminate, without splices to have dimensional stability, on aluminum mandrel.

The test results are shown in fig. 5. There was no warpage on panels with precured skins. There was less warpage on low CTE tools. There was a warpage effect when curing the skins, but it was less extensive and in the opposite direction compared to the phenomenon on panels with only one precured skin. This difference depends upon the different stress situations on the two types of panels (fig. 6). The tensional status is originated by both the different CTE value between the tool and the skin laying on it, and on small differences between the CTE's of the two skins . The difference in the skin CTE's is caused by a different degree of stretching of the fabric fiber. In a fully stretched system, the fiber effect is heavier and the CTE is more fiber-dependent than matrix-dependent. Since the matrix has a CTE much higher than that of the fiber in a stretched system the resulting CTE is lower than in a system that is not completely flattened.

On the panels with one precured skin, the effect is closely related to the linear growth of the tool. The tool side precured skin is under tension, because of the different CTE of the tool. The bag side skin is still uncured, so is capable of flowing. The polymerization crystallizes the skin in an unstressed position at the curing temperature. We get two skins, probably with the same degree of fiber stretching, but differently loaded. During the cooling phase the tool springs back to the original dimensions, unloading the lower skin and loading the upper one. The tensional status of the tool side skin is present both with the aluminum mandrel and with CFRP laminate (tool) on the aluminum mandrel, because the CFRP laminate is elastically loaded by the aluminum tool.

For the panels with both skins uncured, there is a stronger dependency of the phenomenon on the CTE difference of the two skins. The tool deformation elongates the fibers of both skins. The tool side is stretched directly by the tool. The stretching deformation of the upper skin is partially absorbed by the honeycomb core. The polymerization reaction crystallizes an unstressed situation at the curing temperature, but with fibers differently elongated on the two skins. The different orientation of the fibers to the load direction determines a different value of the CTE in the two skins, the upper skin CTE is more matrix-dependent. The resulting CTE in the upper skin is then higher than the CTE in the lower skin, where the coefficient of thermal expansion is more fiber-dependent. The difference of the CTE causes a tensional status opposite to the one present in the panels with one precured skin. This justifies the completely opposite deformation.

Final considerations

Generally when precuring both skins, there are no warpage problems. Naturally this system is more costly and must be utilized only when the precuring of both skins is necessary for engineering requirements or particular fabrication needs. The best compromise between methods of fabrication and costs is the use of a curing cycle. Naturally a low CTE tool will reduce the warpage.

When utilizing aluminum tool, the warpage can be reduced interlaying a CFRP laminate between the lay-up mandrel and the part. Of course, keeping in mind the need of a balanced and symmetrical structure, the warpage phenomenon is contained when the stretching of the tool side layer is kept as low as possible.

It is not mandatory the use of low CTE tool for the fabrication of panel skins, because these parts are fastened all around their periphery at the final assembly stage.

When there is the need of designing structures that are not fully balanced, it may be necessary to utilize fabrication methods and tool materials that can compensate the deformation that would be present also with a whole CFRP tool (no stretching problem).

Sometimes, the need of going through particular fabrication methods and/or utilizing tool materials that can cause warpage, can be compensated by introducing into the tool a "counterwarpage factor" that avoids the deformation on the part. When it is impossible to introduce this factor on the tool, because of the complexity of the shape, the problem of warpage can be reduced through a modification of the lay-up.

The local application of U.D. tape on a panel that is made out mainly of fabric, (and viceversa) can usually correct the profile configuration.

It is very difficult not to have warpage on the first trial. So it is convenient to use an unsophisticated tool and correct the tool or the design after the fabrication of the first part.

REFERENCES

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FIGURE .1. VARIOUS SPLICED LAYERS

FIGURE .2. LINEAR GROWTH OF VARIOUS LAMINATES

FIGURE .3. 8 HARNESS SATIN FABRIC

FIGURE .4. LINEAR GROWTH FOR VARIOUS SPLICED LAYERS CURED ON ALUMINUM TOOL.

FIGURE .5. BOWING VS. VARIOUS MANUFACTURING METHODS

FIGURE .6. STRESS SITUATION OF ONE SKIN PRECURED SANDWICHES AND TWO SKINS COCURED SANDWICHES, MADE WITH O° FABRIC UNSPLICED.

